

TABLE 1

Sl.No.	Phenothiazine derivative	Yield %	m.p. °C	Colour	Formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
1.	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine	75	Characterized as oil	Yellow	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ F ₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	60.50 (60.60)	6.40 (6.46)	8.41 (8.48)
2.	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine dioxalate	80	215	White	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ F ₃ N ₂ O ₁₀ S	51.45 (51.55)	5.30 (5.37)	6.12 (6.22)
3.	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide dioxalate	80	202	White	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ F ₃ N ₂ O ₁₁ S	50.30 (50.36)	5.16 (5.20)	6.01 (6.07)
4.	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide	60	200	White	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ F ₃ N ₂ O ₈ S	46.53 (46.63)	6.26 (6.26)	8.15 (8.21)
5.	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide	50	192	Light yellow	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ F ₃ N ₂ O ₈ S	56.21 (56.28)	5.49 (5.54)	8.87 (8.95)
6.	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide dioxalate	70	191-193 (Foaming with decomp.)	White	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ F ₃ N ₂ O ₁₁ S	48.00 (48.07)	4.58 (4.62)	6.40 (6.46)

poured into water and adjusted to pH 8 with 10% NaOH. The residue was separated and extracted with ether, decolourised and recrystallised to give V as white crystals. V was converted into its dioxalate salt (VI).

Preparation of 2-trifluoromethyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide dioxalate (VI) with perbenzoic acid: A mixture of 2-trifluoromethyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine dioxalate (1.89 g), CHCl₃-EtOH mixture (1:1) (100 ml), perbenzoic acid (10 ml) was stirred at room temp for 40 min and filtered. The resulting precipitate was washed with NaHCO₃ soln. (2%) and crystallized from hot EtOH to give yellow crystals.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (M.A.).

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Synthesis of 6,7-Dimethoxy-3',4'-Methylenedioxy-flavone (Milletenin-C)

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Manuscript received 10 September 1982, accepted 19 July 1983

MILLETENIN-C was isolated as a sticky but tlc pure compound from the leaf extract of *Millettia ovalifolia* along with two other flavonoids, milletenin-A and milletenin-B by Khan and Zaman¹. Its structure as 6,7-dimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyflavone (I) was based on its identity only on tlc with the dehydrogenation product of a natural flavanone, milletenin-A (II). However, no data except m.p. was reported even for the dehydrogenation product.

Jain *et al*² proposed a synthesis for milletenin-C which consists of the oxidation of 2'-hydroxy-4',5'-dimethoxy-3,4-methylenedioxychalkone (III) with selenium dioxide. This communication reports the synthesis of milletenin-C thereby confirming its proposed structure (I). The synthesis was achieved by using 2-(3',4'-methylenedioxy)benzoyloxy-4,5-dimethoxyacetophenone (V) obtained by the esterification of 2-hydroxy-4,5-dimethoxyacetophenone (IV) with 3,4-methylenedioxybenzoyl chloride in presence of pyridine. The ester (V) when treated with KOH in pyridine underwent Baker-Venkataraman migration to give 2-hydroxy-4,5-dimethoxy-3',4'-methy-

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lenedioxy dibenzoyl methane (VI) which on dehydrocyclisation with acetic acid and sodium acetate furnished the required 6,7-dimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyflavone (I), identical with the natural sample.

- (IV) $R^1 - R^2 - H$
 (V) $R^1 - H; R^2 - CO.C_6H_5$
 (VI) $R^1 - CO.C_6H_5$ (3,4-methylenedioxy).
 $R^2 - H$

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord model 577 spectrophotometer.

2-(3',4'-Methylenedioxybenzoyloxy)-4,5-dimethoxyacetophenone (V): A solution of 2-hydroxy-4,5-dimethoxyacetophenone (2.0 g) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was heated with 3,4-methylenedioxybenzoyl chloride (2.24 g) (prepared from 3,4-methylenedioxybenzoic acid, 2.0 g) at 100° for 1 hr and the reaction product was poured in ice-water. Solid crystals separated out, which was filtered, washed with dil.HCl and water, and crystallised from acetone as white crystals, m.p. 175-76°. (Found : C, 62.71 ; H, 4.82. $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 62.79 ; H, 4.68%). It did not give ferric reaction and was insoluble in cold aqueous sodium hydroxide (10%).

2-Hydroxy-4,5-dimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxydibenzoyl methane (VI): A solution of V (2.5 g) in dry pyridine (20 ml) was heated with stirring with powdered potassium hydroxide (3.0 g) at 60°. In about 1 hr the potassium salt of the β -diketone separated out as yellow solid. The stirring was continued for 2 hr more and then acidified with dil. HCl. Yellow solid separated out which was filtered, washed and crystallised from ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 184-185°. (Found : C, 62.74 ; H, 5.01 . $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 62.79 ; H, 4.68%). It gave positive ferric reaction and dissolved in cold aqueous NaOH (10%).

6,7-Dimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyflavone (Milletenin-C) (I): A mixture of the β -diketone (1.0 g),

fused sodium acetate (1.0 g) and glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 hr and then concentrated under reduced pressure to a small volume. It was then poured in ice water. The flavone (0.8 g) separated out and crystallised from amyl alcohol as colourless crystals, m.p. 251-52°(lit.¹, m.p. 252-53°). (Found : C, 66.21; H, 4.41. $C_{18}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 66.25; H, 4.32%). 100 MHz NMR, (TMS as internal standard) ($CDCl_3$, δ): 4.04, 4.06 (s, 6H, $2 \times OCH_3$), 6.12 (s, 2H, O- CH_2 -O), 6.6 (s, 1H, H-3), 7.32-6.74 (m, 3H, aromatic protons), 7.38 (m, 1H, C-5 periproton), 7.58 (m, 1H, H-6'). IR(KBr): 1640 ($>C=O$), 1610, 1510 cm^{-1} (aromatic $C=C$).

Acknowledgement

The authors sincerely thank Prof. A. C. Jain for providing a sample of milletenin-C and the U.G.C., New Delhi for a Teacher Fellowship to one of them (S.P.M.).

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Nitrogen Heterocyclic Analogous of Cannabinoids. Part-I : Synthesis of 6H-Indolo[1,2-C] [1,3]-benzoxazine Systems and Evaluation of Their Biological Activities

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Manuscript received 16 November 1981, revised 11 March 1983, accepted 1 September 1983

EFFORTS have recently been made to prepare nitrogen containing analogous of the cannabinoids to modify the pharmacological profile. Pyridobenzoxazine derivatives (I), synthesized by Nitya Anand *et al*^{1,2} as a model compound, containing a nitrogen atom at the ring junction of the pyran and alicyclic ring of tetrahydrocannabinol seemed to be of great interest for studying structure-activity relationship in this class of compounds. It was, therefore, thought that molecules having mixed features of cannabinoids (rings A and B) and that of

indole nucleus with nitrogen as part of both ring B and C would be of pharmacological interest. This

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